

Some Properties of Quantum Shannon's Entropy Density

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In this note, we examine the behaviour of Shannon's entropy density for some examples in quantum mechanics.

We start with a quasiparticle probability $P(x \text{ and } p) = W(x) f_p \exp(ipx)$ (where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction given by $\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)$) and obtain a Shannon's entropy (after summing on p):

$$\text{Total entropy density} = -P(x) \ln(P(x)) - P(p) \ln(P(p)) - W(x) \times d/dx W(x) \quad ((1))$$

It may be noted that if $f(p)=f(-p)$ ((1)) may also be written as:

$$\text{Total entropy density} = -P(x) \ln(P(x)) - P(p) \ln(P(p)) - \int p \, d/dp \, f_p$$

We consider the cases of a particle in a box with an infinite potential at the walls and the harmonic oscillator ground state. Finally we consider the influence of $u(x) = [d/dx W(x)]/W(x)$ on the spatial change of Shannon's spatial entropy as $W(x)$ and $u(x)$ are often periodic and this leads to a periodic entropy density. In general, entropy is obtained by integrating the entropy density and one may question whether one should examine the density at all. In (1), however, entropy density is considered and it seems that there are some interesting properties of Shannon's entropy density in quantum systems. Furthermore, there has been some recent work in the literature which makes use of entropy density to create an extra potential term for the Schrodinger equation in cases of temperature.

Shannon's Entropy Density

A number of articles in the literature use Shannon's spatial entropy $-2W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)]$ or momentum entropy $-P(p)\ln[P(p)]$ where $P(p)=f_p*f_p$. Here, as mentioned above, we use ((1)) based on a quasiparticle probability. The third term represents the covariance function used in the derivation of the Cramer Rao inequality linking the variance of x with Fisher information (2). In addition, we use the following equation, obtained from $d/dx (WW) = 2Wu(x)$ for the change in entropy density $s(x)$ (3):

$$d/dx s(x) = 2 u(x) s(x) - 2 W(x)W(x) u(x) \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } s(x) = -W(x)W(x) \ln[W(x)] \quad ((1a))$$

$$d/dp s(p) = 2 u(p) s(p) - 2 f_p*f_p u(p) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } s(p) = -2 f_p*f_p \ln(f_p) \text{ and } u(p) = [d/dp f_p]/f_p \quad ((1b))$$

Note: In ((1a)) $s(x)$ is Shannon's spatial entropy. The third term of ((1)) is an additional spatial term which is part of the overall entropy density.

Particle in a Box with Infinite Potential Walls

In such a case, $W(x) = C \sin(kx - b)$ where C and b are constants and $k = 6.28 n/L$ where L is the length of the box. Here k is the root mean square momentum. We argued in (4) that quantum mechanics in a bound state is based on $\exp(ipx)$, the description of a free quantum particle. In a potential, it is suggested the quantum particle would scatter leading to a conditional probability of $P(p/x) = \sum_p f_p \exp(ipx) / [\sum_p f_p \exp(ipx)]$. The denominator, which is a normalization factor, is called the wavefunction. It has the property that it changes infinitesimally in space and momentum space like $\exp(ipx)$ except that p and x are replaced by conditional averages of p and x where:

$$\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle = [\sum_p p f_p \exp(ipx)] / W(x) \text{ and a similar condition for } \langle x \text{ conditional} \rangle \quad ((4))$$

Note that even if $f(p) = f(-p)$, $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ is not zero. We argue the wavefunction tries to mimic the behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$. In the case of a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, it mimics it almost identically, producing an $\exp(i \text{pave } x) - \exp(-i \text{pave } x)$. The f_p part, however, is different.

For the simple case of $W(x) = C \sin(kx)$, we see Shannon's spatial entropy density $s(x)$ is:

$$s(x) = C^* C \sin(kx) \sin(kx) [2 \ln(C) + 2 \ln(\sin(kx))] \quad ((5))$$

For x approaching zero, $s(x)$ is zero. As x increases slightly ((1a)) suggests:

$$d/dx s(x) = 2C^* C kx^* kx [2 \ln(C) + 2 \ln(kx)] u(x) - 2 C^* C kx^* kx u(x) \quad ((6))$$

Alternatively, one may write ((1a)) as:

$$d/dx s(x) = 2 W(x)W(x) u(x) [-2 \ln(W) - 1 + 2 \ln(C)] \quad ((7))$$

There would be turning points, i.e. $d/dx s(x) = 0$, for $W(x) = 0$, $d/dx W(x) = 0$ and $[-2 \ln(W) - 1 + 2 \ln(C)] = 0$. It is possible to add the third term of ((1)) to ((7)) and obtain a different turning point for the term in []. In particular:

Extra spatial entropy density term = $- W(x)W(x) u(x) x$ so:

$$d/dx \text{ Extra spatial entropy density term} = -2 W(x)W(x) u(x)u(x) - W(x)W(x) u(x) - W(x)W(x) x d/dx u(x) \quad ((7b))$$

The second form of ((1)), however, shows the third term of ((1)) may be written in terms of momentum and it will then augment Shannon's momentum entropy.

((7)) shows $d/dx s(x)$ is proportional to $W(x)$ and $d/dx W(x)$. Thus, one might expect the entropy to reach a stationary point when $W(x)=0$ or when $d/dx W(x)=0$. This seems to suggest periodic behaviour of $s(x)$. Furthermore, one may note that for $[-2\ln(W) - 1 + 2\ln(C)]$, if $W(x)$ is of the order of kx for $\sin(kx)$ near $x=0$ then $-2\ln(W)$ will be a large positive number which gets smaller as x increases. When it reaches a value of 1, it will no longer cause $d/dx s(x)$ to increase, but will start to decrease it. (This behaviour is more interesting when applied to the ground state of the oscillator.)

One may inquire into the form of a second order change in Shannon's spatial density i.e.

$$d/dx d/dx s(x) = (-\ln(WW) - 1)[2(Wu)^2 - 2m^2v(x)^2 WW] - 4 WW u^2$$

Thus, if $u(x)=0$ causing $d/dx s(x)=0$, the second order change is at this point:

$(-\ln(WW) - 1)[-2m^2v(x)^2 WW]$ which is proportional to spatial density and classical kinetic energy.

One may also consider f_p . From (5), it is given by (for $n=1$):

$$f_p = C \cos(ap) / (E - p^2/2m) \quad ((7c))$$

Then $d/dp s(p)$ is proportional to:

$$f_p \cdot f_p u(p) \text{ proportional to } (E - p^2/2m) \sin(ap)\cos(ap) + \cos(ap)\cos(ap) p/m$$

A second factor affecting $d/dp s(p)$ is $[\ln(|\cos(ap)|) - 2 \ln(|E - p^2/2m|) + \ln(C) - 1]$.

If p is tiny compared to E , then the first term dominates and one has again the $\sin(ap)\cos(ap)$ periodic behaviour. When $p^2/2m$ is close to E , the term $\cos(ap)\cos(ap) p/m$ dominates and one has only $\cos(ap)$ periodicity.

Ground State of the Harmonic Oscillator

First of all, one may note that for this case, $s(x)$ is proportional to potential energy density $W(x)W(x)V(x)$ where $V(x)=.5kx^2$. Using ((7)), one may note that $s(x)=0$ at $x=0$ for the oscillator. If one chooses m and k such that $C=1$ one (for the sake of argument), then $d/dx s(x)=0$ when $-2\ln(W) - 1 = 0$. Using $W(x)=\exp(-.5\sqrt{mk} x^2)$, this leads to an x such that:

$$.5kx^2 = .5 \sqrt{k/m} = \text{ground state energy} \quad ((8))$$

Thus, this x point at which $d/dx s(x)=0$ corresponds to the endpoint where classical velocity = 0 and all energy is potential energy. Thus, $s(x)=0$ when there is no potential energy and $d/dx s(x)=0$ when all energy is potential energy. It is almost as if $s(x)$ is increasing as $V(x)$ increases, but as seen for the particle in the box, this already happens as one moved up a hump of $\sin(kx)$ with no potential present.

Consider the third term in ((1)) i.e. $-W(x) \times d/dx W(x) = \exp(-\sqrt{mk} x^2) (x^2 \sqrt{mk})$. Thus, as $d/dx s(x) > 0$, i.e. $s(x)$ increases as one moves away from $x=0$, the third term also augments the overall entropy. Note: $s(x)$ only pertains to $-2W(x)W(x)\ln[W(x)]$, while the third term is part of an overall entropy density. This third term increases as potential increases, but does not have any turning point. If one uses ((7b)), the turning point will no longer be at the point where classical velocity is zero. In such a case, one has for ((7b))

$(x-2) W(x)W(x) u(x)$ so $(-2 \ln(W) - 1 + x-2)=0$ yields the new turning point. This leads to the quadratic equation $-\sqrt{mk} x^2 - 3 + x = 0$. ((1)) also shows the extra term in the entropy density may be written in terms of momentum. In that case, it would affect the momentum part instead of the spatial.

For the oscillator ground state, $f_p = 1/(2.14 m w)^{25} \exp(-p^2/(2mw))$ $\hbar=1$ and $w=\sqrt{k/m}$

Thus, the normalization constant is different, as is the constant in the exponential, but otherwise the form is the same as one considers $d/dp s(p)$. If one were to manipulate m and k differently to make the new normalization constant 1, then ((7)) would lead to:

$$-2 \ln(f_p) - 1 = 0 \text{ which leads to } 1/2m p^2 = .5 \sqrt{k/m} = E \text{ ground state.}$$

Thus, in both cases, one has similar behaviour. Shannon's momentum entropy density is 0 at $p=0$ and has a stationary point at the maximum kinetic energy, where potential energy is 0.

The Case of Oscillations

First note that $u(x) = [d/dx W(x)] / W(x)$ seems to play an important role in quantum mechanics. It is proportional to the change of $d/dx s(x)$ as shown in ((3)), but also appears in:

$$d/dx [W(x)W(x)] = 2 W(x)W(x) u(x) \quad ((9)) \text{ and}$$

$$(-1/2m)(d/dx)^3 W(x) / W(x) - .5mv(x)v(x) u(x) = F(x) \quad ((10))$$

Where $v(x)$ is classical velocity given by $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ and $F(x)$ force.

The change in Shannon's spatial entropy density is proportional to $W(x)W(x)$, the density and $u(x)$ which is proportional to $d/dx W(x)$ (from ((7))). In fact, $d/dx s(x)$ follows from $d/dx (WW) = 2(WW) u(x)$, so it is not a surprise these two factors have an important impact on $d/dx s(x)$. The third term in ((1)) also is dependent on $(W(x)W(x))$ the spatial density and $u(x)$.

In many problems $W(x)$ is periodic so there are turning points for $s(x)$ when $W(x)=0$ and $d/dx W(x)=0$. Thus, $s(x)$ seems to be periodic. $u(x)$ is the conditional average momentum, so if this is zero, the entropy stops changing at this point. If $W(x)=0$, it seems entropy density is zero, but also $d/dx s(x)$ is zero to first order. $\langle p \text{ conditional} \rangle$ is not zero, so this leads to a change in density which creates a change in entropy. As argued in previous notes, $W(x)$ tries to mimic the behaviour of $\exp(ipx)$. For a bound state, $W(x)$ will be real, but periodic in a number of cases. Thus, this intrinsic periodic behaviour in quantum mechanics seems to be linked to periodic spatial entropy density. Similar arguments, it seems hold for the spatial Shannon's momentum entropy density.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to investigate Shannon's spatial entropy density for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, the ground state oscillator and periodic wavefunctions. It seems $u(x) = [d/dx W(x)] / W(x)$ and its momentum counterpart as well as density $W(x)W(x)$ drive changes in entropy density, and as both are periodic and have zeros, the entropy density seems to be also periodic. It is interesting to note $d/dx W(x) = 0$ for high energies marks the peak points where the classical envelope density function may touch the quantum one. Thus, these are turning points for entropy density as well. It seems, however, that one cannot apply the correspondence principle at such a point to calculate the change in entropy, even though such a result can be written strictly in terms of density.

For the case of the ground state oscillator, spatial entropy density, which is proportional to potential energy density $V(x) W(x)W(x)$, increases as potential energy increases, but $d/dx s(x)$ is zero (for a specific choice of m and k yielding a normalization constant of 1) at the classical endpoint of the oscillator. It should be noted, however, that entropy also increases for a particle in a box with a $\sin(kx)$ type wavefunction as x moves away from zero, even though there is no potential.

References

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